

Ion Exchange Properties of Zirconium Molybdate and Zirconium Tungstate—I

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Zirconium molybdate and tungstate were obtained by adding aqueous solution of zirconium oxychloride to aqueous solutions of ammonium molybdate and sodium tungstate. *pH*-metric studies reveal that both the materials exhibit ion exchange properties. The thermogravimetric analysis of the samples indicate that both the exchanger materials contain about 11-12% of hydrated water which is released slowly within the temperature range 90 to 240° in case of zirconium molybdate and within 80 to 180° in the case of zirconium tungstate. The sorption of amines of Zn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Ni(II) on the above exchangers have been studied at different ionic concentrations of the external solutions. In each case the sorption increases with increase in the external concentration (0.01 to 0.10*M*), attains a maximum at 0.10*M* and then decreases with further increase in the concentration. The sorption capacity, q_A , follows the order :

Zn(II)-amine > Cu(II)-amine > Cd(II)-amine > Ni(II)-amine.

A survey of the available literature¹⁻⁶ indicates an inadequate understanding of the ion exchange properties of zirconium molybdate and zirconium tungstate. A few interesting separations have been described by using these materials as ion exchangers⁴⁻⁶. This paper incorporates a more systematic study of the ion exchange properties of these materials starting from their method of preparation. The paper includes, in brief, the study of the following aspects :

- (i) Preparation of the exchanger material and determination of time required for maximum exchange, i.e. the equilibration period,
- (ii) Thermogravimetric analysis of the samples,
- (iii) *pH*-metric studies,
- (iv) Determination of the sorption capacity, q_A , using some divalent metallic ammine complexes at their varying concentrations in the external solution, and
- (v) Effect of the addition of the buffering agent on the exchange capacity q_A .

Experimental

All the reagents used, unless otherwise stated, were of the C. P. Grade. All the experiments were carried out in doubly distilled water.

Preparation of the exchanger materials :

(a) *Zirconium molybdate* : Zirconium molybdate was prepared by adding slight excess of ammonium molybdate to an aqueous solution of zirconium oxychloride in basic medium (*pH*=8.0). The precipitate thus obtained was washed free of the Cl⁻ ions and dried at 40°. The dried precipitate was brought to the required particle size by grinding and sieving.

(b) *Zirconium tungstate* : Zirconium tungstate was obtained by adding slight excess of sodium tungstate solution to an aqueous solution of zirconium oxychloride. The precipitate thus obtained was worked out as above.

Preparation of the stock solution of amines : Stock solutions of ammine complexes of the metal ions Zn(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Ni(II) of different ionic concentrations were prepared by dissolving required quantities of their water soluble salts in aqueous ammonia (1 : 4). The *pH* of the solutions were adjusted to 10.0 by the addition of 1 : 4 ammonia solution or 0.10 *M* HCl solution.

Determination of the metal ion content : The metal ion contents of the solutions were determined by applying standard complexometric titration method⁷. Copper was determined by the standard iodometric method.

Determination of the exchange capacity q_A : A typical procedure is described below. 25 ml of the stock solution containing a test metal ion of the specified pH and ionic concentration was introduced into a stoppered conical flask containing 250 mg of the exchanger material and the mixture was shaken for a predetermined period (3 hours in case of zirconium molybdate and 4 hours in case of zirconium tungstate). The equilibrated supernatant liquid containing the unadsorbed metal ion was separated from the solid exchanger by centrifugation and its total metallic content was determined complexometrically. Knowing the concentration of the exchanging ion initially and after equilibration, the amount exchanged in the exchanger material (q_A) was determined.

Method for pH titration : 5 gms each of the two exchangers was converted into H-form completely by repeated exchange with 1 M HCl solution. A procedure, in brief, is described below. The samples of the zirconium molybdate and tungstate were introduced into stoppered conical flasks and shaken with 50 ml of 1 M HCl for half an hour; the sample was separated from acid by decantation and washed thrice with double-distilled water by decantation method. To this sample 50 ml of 1 M HCl was again added and the procedure

repeated five times. The sample thus obtained was introduced into column and 100 ml of 1 M HCl passed through it at the rate of 1 ml/min. Finally the sample was washed thoroughly with double distilled water to remove any free acid adhered to the sample and dried at 40°.

One gram of this sample was taken in a 100 ml beaker, added with 50 ml of double distilled water and titrated against 0.20 M NaOH solution pH-metrically. NaOH was added in fractions of 0.10 ml through a micro burette and after each addition of NaOH the beaker was shaken mechanically till constant pH was obtained.

Results and Discussion

The results of these investigations are presented in Tables 1 and 2, the pH-titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. A perusal of the data reveal the following points :

1. From Fig. 1 it is seen that the volume of 0.20 M NaOH required to raise the pH of the free acid solution is much less than the amount of NaOH required to raise the pH of the solution containing one gram of zirconium molybdate and zirconium tungstate from pH 6 to 10 in each case.

TABLE 1—TIME OF SHAKING vs AMOUNT EXCHANGED ON Zr-MOLYBDATE AND Zr-TUNGSTATE
 AMOUNT OF THE EXCHANGER MATERIAL = 250 mg
 TOTAL VOLUME = 25 ml
 CONCENTRATION OF THE EXTERNAL SOLUTION = 0.10M
 pH OF THE SOLUTION = 9.5

Time of shaking (in hours)	Amount exchanged (in m. equiv.)							
	Zr-Molybdate				Zr-Tungstate			
	Zn(II)-ammine	Cu(II)-ammine	Cd(II)-ammine	Ni(II)-ammine	Zn(II)-ammine	Cu(II)-ammine	Cd(II)-ammine	Ni(II)-ammine
1.0	0.164	0.046	0.033	0.033	0.184	0.038	0.030	0.030
2.0	0.185	0.080	0.046	0.037	0.208	0.065	0.050	0.045
3.0	0.300	0.150	0.056	0.054	0.224	0.084	0.080	0.068
4.0	0.300	0.150	0.056	0.07	0.265	0.099	0.097	0.081
5.0	0.300	0.150	0.056	0.087	0.265	0.099	0.097	0.081

TABLE 2 - CONCENTRATION vs AMOUNT EXCHANGED ON Zr-MOLYBDATE AND Zr-TUNGSTATE
 AMOUNT OF THE EXCHANGER MATERIAL = 250 mg
 TOTAL VOLUME = 25 ml.
 pH OF THE EQUILIBRIUM SOLUTION = 9.5

Concentration (in M)	Amount exchanged (in m. equiv.)							
	Zr-molybdate				Zr-tungstate			
	Zn(II)-ammine	Cu(II)-ammine	Cd(II)-ammine	Ni(II)-ammine	Zn(II)-ammine	Cu(II)-ammine	Cd(II)-ammine	Ni(II)-ammine
0.01	0.163	0.037	0.034	0.033	0.148	0.060	0.048	0.040
0.02	0.163	0.060	0.038	0.033	0.200	0.067	0.052	0.040
0.05	0.220	0.067	0.048	0.037	0.224	0.075	0.057	0.054
0.075	0.240	0.12	0.049	0.054	0.224	0.090	0.082	0.054
0.10	0.300	0.150	0.098	0.087	0.265	0.097	0.089	0.081
0.15	0.220	0.135	0.053	0.054	0.204	0.060	0.055	0.054
0.20	0.180	0.075	0.047	0.054	0.143	0.045	0.055	0.054

Fig. 1. pH-METRIC TITRATION CURVE

2. The thermogravimetric analysis reveals that both the exchangers contain about 11 to 12% of hydrated water which is lost slowly within the range 90 to 240° in case of zirconium molybdate and 80 to 180° in case of zirconium tungstate.

3. From Table 1 it is clear that the time required for complete sorption is 3 hours and 4 hours in case of exchange with zirconium molybdate and zirconium tungstate respectively.

4. Data in Table 2 indicate that the value of the sorption capacity, q_A , increases with increase in the external concentration, attains a maximum and then decreases with further increase in concentration.

5. The Zn(II)-ammine complex has the greatest sorption capacity (Table 2) at all concentrations in both the exchanger materials. Other amines follow the order :

Zn(II)-ammine > Cu(II)-ammine > Cd(II)-ammine > Ni(II)-ammine.

6. The addition of the buffering agent decreases the sorption capacity, q_A , in general.

Recently, inorganic cation exchangers with much more satisfactory properties have been prepared by combining Group IV oxides with more acidic Group V and Group VI oxides⁸⁻¹⁰. In case of zirconium molybdate, tungstate and phosphate the ratio of Mo/Zr, W/Zr and P/Zr has been found to be equal to 2. The materials prepared by us have been found to be insoluble in the acidic as well as in the basic medium under which the experiments have been carried out (pH 1 to 12). However, they are completely soluble in highly acidic medium (~2 M HCl). In analogy with the known structure of zirconium phosphate, probable structures to the zirconium molybdate and tungstate may be assigned

as $O_3MoO-Zr-OMoO_3$ and $O_3WO-Zr-OWO_3$, respectively.

Analysis of the pH-titration curve (Fig. 1): From pH-metric titrations the consumption of more amount of NaOH when the solution to be titrated contained the solid zirconium molybdate and tungstate seems to be utilized for the neutralisation of the mobile (exchangeable) H^+ ions attached to the solids. The analysis of the curve show that both the exchangers are of the weak acid type and the exchange is very slow as after each addition of the NaOH fraction (0.10 ml) the beaker had to be shaken for about half an hour to obtain constant pH value.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The thermogravimetric analysis of the samples indicates the presence of about 11 to 12% of the hydrated water which is lost very slowly within the temperature range 90 to 240° in case of zirconium molybdate and within the range 80 to 180° in case of zirconium tungstate. There is no evidence for the decomposition of the solids within the temperature range studied. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on the 'SETRAM' thermogravimetric analyser obtained from France.

Determination of the equilibration time: The time required for the maximum exchange of a particular ion has been determined by equilibrating the exchanger materials with the exchanging ions for different periods of time. Minimum time required for the maximum exchange has been taken as the equilibration time.

Effect of exchanging ion concentration: The decrease in the sorption capacity, q_A , at higher external concentrations of the exchanging ions (Table 2) is presumably due to the possible lowering of the ionic activity at higher concentrations. A diminution of the exchange potential at higher concentrations is well known¹¹.

Effect of the nature of the exchanging ion: Ionic potential (charge/radius), of the exchanging ion is mainly responsible for its relative exchange-rate. Since all the ions under study have identical formal charge of +2, the rate of exchange should solely depend upon the size of the complex ion. Simple ionic radii of the metal ions involved are in the order¹²: Cu^{2+} , 0.72 Å, Zn^{2+} 0.74 Å, Ni^{2+} , 0.78 Å and Cd^{2+} , 0.97 Å. But the symmetry of the various amines has also to be considered before making an estimate about the relative sizes of these metal-ammines. $[Zn(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$ and $[Cd(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$ are tetrahedral, $[Cu(NH_3)_4]^{2+}$ is distorted square planar and $[Ni(NH_3)_6]^{2+}$ is octahedral^{12,13}. Since the tetrahedral geometry involves a more compact structure than either of square-planar or octahedral geometries, the ionic sizes of these metal amines are expected to follow

the order :

Zn(II)-ammine < Cu(II)-ammine < Cd(II)-ammine < Ni(II)-ammine.

The values of ionic potential, ϕ (charge/radius), will, therefore be in the reverse order. Observed sequence in the q_A values for different amines follows the order of the ϕ values^{1,4} as expected.

Effect of addition of the buffering agent : This study was carried out to obtain the lower pH values in which ammine complexes remain soluble in the external solution. Normally, the complexes are decomposed at pH 8.0 in the absence of the buffering agent while they remain soluble when buffering agents are added even at pH 8.0. It has been observed that the addition of the buffering agent decreases the q_A values in all the cases which may be due to the increase in the competing NH_4^+ ions.

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